

LONG TERM EVALUATION OF VASCULARIZED FIBULAR GRAFT AS TREATMENT AFTER RESECTION OF GIANT CELL TUMOR (GCT) AT RIGHT PROXIMAL HUMERUS: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT Giant cell tumors are locally aggressive tumors with high rate of recurrence. Recurrences of GCT in autogenous fibular grafts have been rarely reported and pathological fractures through such grafts are even rarer. Wide excision is the management of choice, but this creates a defect at bone. The preferred modalities for the defect reconstruction include vascularized/non-vascularized bone graft, osteoarticular allografts and custom-made prosthesis. We present our experience with wide resection and vascularized autogenous fibula grafting for GCT of proximal humerus.

KEYWORDS Giant cell tumor, GCT, Vascularized Fibular Graft, Proximal Humerus

Introduction

Giant cell tumours are locally aggressive tumours with a high rate of recurrence. Recurrences of GCT in autogenous fibular grafts have been rarely reported, and pathological fractures through such grafts are even rarer. Wide excision is the management of choice, but this creates a defect at the bone. The preferred modalities for the defect reconstruction include vascularized/non-vascularized bone graft, osteoarticular allografts and custom-made prosthesis. We present our experience with wide resection and vascularized autogenous fibula grafting for GCT of the proximal humerus.

History

Male, 34 years old presented at Orthopaedic Clinic Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital Makassar, with a lump at right up-

per arm since three months before the visit date. Lump was later confirmed as Giant Cell Tumor (GCT) from radiologic and histopathologic evaluation. Vascularized fibular graft procedure was performed following resection of GCT at right proximal humerus.

Interesting points for discussion

Upper limb function after resection of GCT at proximal humerus depends on reconstruction technique to conserve shoulder joint stability and good elbow joint function.

We preferred vascularized fibular graft as reconstruction modality followed by sling procedure, in which long head of biceps brachii attached to bone graft to maintain the continuity of fibular head to preserve shoulder joint stability. We attached the peroneal artery and vein to circumflex humeral artery and vein.

Solution and Rational

Resection of the tumor followed by vascularized fibular graft to proximal humerus to preserve good shoulder stability. We evaluated anatomical, functional and radiological outcomes of this patient after treatment.

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Figure 1. A 34 year old otherwise healthy male presented with lump at right shoulder. Radiologic finding showed bone tumor on right proximal humerus.

Figure 4. Post operative x-ray of humerus showed fibular graft on right proximal humerus (A). Follow up on 8 months after surgery showed minimal callus formation (B). Two years follow up showed complete union of fibular graft (C).

Figure 2. A cricket ball sized mass removed from proximal humerus (A). A large bone defect that need to repair is seen (B).

Figure 5. Post operation clinical evaluation showed limited range of motion on the right arm. Forward flexion and extension were limited (A & B). External rotation and internal rotation were limited (C & D). Abduction was limited (E)

Figure 3. Clinical appearance after surgery, stitches have been removed

Figure 6. Pictures showed daily activities performed after fibular graft operation. Despite of limitation on right shoulder's range of motion following fibular graft operation, patient was still able to perform daily basic functions. Take on and off of cloth (A), drink from bottle (B), eat using hand (C), writing (D)

Final outcome

After two years follow up, the patient has a good functional outcome with no recurrence of tumour and the graft has radiologically united. The outcome is satisfactory with no further symptom nor complaint of dexterity.

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